

1 **Phosphatase activation in TNBC.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Phosphatases were present both in small and large quantities, and activated in resistance. *PTPRU*,
8 *PTPRN*, *PTPRO*, *ENPP2*, and *PPP2R2C* were among the phosphatases most dramatically activated.

9 Citations

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